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Board Diversity And Performance Of Consumer Goods Firms In Nigeria

¹EDWIN-UREBE, E. Chinelo. & ²Dr. OBIORA, Fabian

^{1&2}Department of Accountancy,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the board diversity and performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. for the period of 2012-2023. The specific objectives were to; determine the effect of age diversity, gender diversity, ethnic diversity and Foreign diversity on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The variables were financial performance as the dependent variables while age diversity, gender diversity, ethnic diversity and Foreign diversity were the independent variables. Panel Least Squared (PLS) method of data analysis was used. *Expo facto* research design was employed in this study. The data were of secondary nature and were sourced from the annual report of the selected consumer goods firms. The study also employed descriptive statistics, Hausman test and correlation in this study. From the analysis result the study found that, age diversity has significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. (t-test 3.620103, p=0.0004) gender diversity has significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria, (t-test 2.88188, p=0.0015), Ethnic diversity has no significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. (t-test 1.396590, p=0.6182). The study concluded that board diversity variables (age diversity, gender diversity, ethnic diversity and Foreign diversity) significantly influenced changes in the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study recommended that the management of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria should continue to balance the level of age diversity in order to improve their return on assets and balance decision value. Gender diversity should be increased between 3-4 members for improved quality and quick decision making in relation to performance. Ethnic representations on the board will be good since many studies show that board ethnic and international diversity improves firm performance.

Keywords: board diversity, Age diversity, Gender diversity, Ethnic diversity and Foreign diversity

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Diversity is a sizzling topic in the world of corporate governance with the board leadership in agreement about the benefits of a diverse board. In recent corporate governance research, board diversity and their relation to firm performance has received major attention (Makhlouf, Laili, Basah and Siam, 2015). Across the globe, the concept of board diversity has caught the attention of many people including policy makers, shareholders, investors and even researchers (Ekadah, & Mboya, 2015). The board of directors is crucial in overseeing and crafting strategic decisions, contributing to the establishment of the company's vision and mission (Mgammal, 2022), and thus serving the interests of diverse stakeholders. It not only

helps to eliminate an ineffective management team but also assists the enterprise interconnectivity linkages to the external environment and facilitates acquiring external resources.

The diverse structure of the board of directors, as the top leadership team of a company, can provide the organization with a variety of perspectives, insights, knowledge, and experience that can inspire the board to better perform its duties. However, there is no consensus on the definition of boardroom diversity (Behlau et al., 2024). The board of directors has gained a significant role in corporate governance owing to its different attributes (SierraMorán et al., 2024). In recent years, corporate boards have increasingly changed regarding director attributes such as age, gender, education, expertise, and so on. For example, the representation of females in the top 100 fortune firms' corporate boards has increased from 16.8% in 2004 to 26% in 2018 (Chen et al., 2023; Deloitte, 2019; Ting et al., 2021). However, the tendency for a more diversified corporate board has raised the following questions over time:

Diversity in a corporate board has the tendency to bring about a robust wealth of experience, skills, different perspectives and other qualities into a single pool which could further enhance quality decision making. The multicultural organisation usually has an edge in the selection and retention of top personnel (Mazur & Bialostocka, 2010). Hambrick and Mason (1984), discovered that top management heterogeneity has a greater tendency to increase firms' performance. Therefore, heterogeneity has become imperative for complex, large business operations in terms of quality decision making. Board diversity is a broad concept which cuts across expertise, managerial backgrounds, age, learning style, gender, language, education, ethnicity, culture (Swartz, & Firer, 2005). Directors of firms have different varying important characteristics, personality and background, like the functional and educational background, varying skills, experience in industry, insider status race, gender, (Ferreira, 2010).

These attributes are necessary in order to maintain objectivity and independence among the board members. In addition, this quality enables various; perception, interpretations, vast skills, knowledge, and experience to be rough to the table as a result of various background (Nederveen, Van Knippenberg, & Van Dierendonck, 2013). The board of directors is entrusted with crucial economic decisions. The quality of decision-making is likely to depend on skills, reputation and other characteristics of the directors as on the interaction between the directors.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine board Diversity and performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This study specifically identified the following objectives:

- i. To determine the effect of Age diversity on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- ii. To evaluate the effect of gender diversity on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- iii. To assess the effect of ethnic diversity on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- iv. To examine the effect of Foreign Diversity on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses are formulated

Ho₁: Age diversity has no significant effect on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Ho₂: Gender diversity affects the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria

Ho₃: Ethnic diversity has no significant effect on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Ho₄: Foreign diversity has no significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Board Diversity

Board diversity is the proportion of women, ethnic, racial minorities (people who are not Anglo-Australians) on the board (Wang and Cliff, 2009). Marimuthu (2008) define corporate board diversity as the disparity in terms of age, race, ethnicity, gender and socio-cultural identities within a group in a specific corporation. It has also been defined as the composition of corporate board with a distinct combination of attributes, skills and characteristics which the members poses (Vanderbilt, Walt & Ingle, 2003). The Australian Multicultural Foundation (2010) defined the term diversity as significant

differences between people, including perceptions of differences that need to be considered in particular situations and circumstances. Often the most significant differences are the least obvious, such as our thinking styles or beliefs and values. They gave multiple dimensions of diversity which may be more or less significant depending on the nature of the organization. These include gender, age, culture, ethnicity, regional culture, sexual orientation, mental and physical abilities, education, religion, language, literacy, work experience, functional role and status, economic status, family status, career roles, geographic location, work style, communication style, learning style, thinking style, management style personality, ideology, profession, and industry.

2.1.2 Financial Performance

The financial performance of publicly traded corporations on the capital market is important; it is also seen as a platform for attracting capital and lowering a company's cost of capital. A corporation with a very high-pitched financial performance will, in reality, gain a favorable reputation among Investors. At the same time, the capital market, managers, and investors rely on audited financial reports to make decisions about a company's business efficiency. As a result, better financial reporting will have a favorable impact on the company's financial performance. The term financial performance is described as multifaceted (Santos & Brito, 2023). Many scholars have used a variety of ways to quantify financial performance. The financial performance of the organization will be examined in this study based on its profitability. Profitability is always calculated as the ratio of pre-tax income to shareholder equity (Chen & Chen, 2023).

Profitability is quantified in a variety of ways, including Return on Assets (ROA), Price Earnings Ratio (PER), and Return on Equity (ROE). The key metric of financial performance used in this study is cash value added which is a contemporary accounting measure. Financial Performance is a measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business to generate revenues (Abakasanga, Ogbonna, & Umobong, 2022). It is used to describe the state of affairs of a firm. The term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period (Abakasanga, Ogbonna, & Umobong, 2022). According to Abraham, Zhang, Joseph, Agyemang and Ofori (2021) financial performance are measured in various ways, such as shareholders' wealth maximization, profitability, and components of financial statements including sales, assets, liability and equity.

Company performance is concerned with the whole health status of the company finance or otherwise. Traditionally, the analysis of the performance of a firm is usually a bench on financial performance indicators, but nowadays there is a broader view to its evaluation by the inclusion of non-financial performance indicators such as corporate social responsibility, organizational reputation, innovation/technology, employee morale and research and development. This research would only take financial performance into consideration. (Santoss, Ledur & Brito, 2023), in their work classified modern firm performance into strategic performance and financial performance. The strategic performance was classified into customer satisfaction, employee satisfaction, social responsibility and environmental responsibility.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Resource Dependent Theory

Resource dependent theory was developed by (Pfeffer 1972; Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). The theory visualizes a firm as an open system that does not operate in a vacuum and depends on the firm's external environment. Hence, the firms must engage in partnerships with the outside environment. These partnerships help the firm to build relationships with outside entities and environments. The board of directors of the firm and other senior management is depicted as a means to manage the external dependency of the firm. Therefore, the board and management manage to reduce transaction costs and manage the uncertainty that comes with the interaction with the external environment.

Since the firms operate in an open system, they must acquire resources and other necessities from the outside environment creating an interdependency with outside entities (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978; de Cabo et al., 2012). This theory values the roles other stakeholders play in giving a platform for the firm to get necessary resources by partnering with relevant constituencies (Lawal, 2012). In addition, this theory

views the board of directors' boundary spanners of the organization. The board, therefore, is vital in bringing forth the necessary linkages with the external environment of the firm. A gender-diverse board allows the female directors bring onboard unique skills, knowledge, and experiences different and distinct from their male counterparts (Jamali, Safieddine, and Daouk, 2007).

According to Johnson (1996), the resource-dependent theory focuses on selecting representatives for firms that will provide a gateway for firms to gain resources. Access to resources is crucial for a firm's success. Furthermore, for firms to survive, the organization must exert control of access to resources in its environment. Therefore, a more gender-diverse board and management influence to a great extent the firm performance.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ime, Chukwu and Chukwu (2024) explored the nexus between board diversity and firm performance in quoted Commercial banks in Nigeria. The population of the study made up of 23 listed banks in the Nigerian stock exchange in 2022. The study adopts judgemental sampling technique to select 10 quoted commercial banks as the sample study. Ex-post facto research design was implemented and secondary data were obtained from quoted commercial banks for the period of five years (2018-2022), making up 50 firm-year sample observations. The study adopts descriptive statistics for univariate analysis, bivariate for correlation analysis, while the hypotheses were tested using the multiple regression analysis based on Excel Analytical package 2018 and SPSS version 20. The findings are as follows: the first model shows that board diligence and board gender diversity are positively, statistically and significantly correlated with earning per share in commercial banks in Nigeria. The second model indicates that board diligence and board size are positively, statistically and significantly associated with share price in commercial banks in Nigeria.

Aziekwe and Okegbe, (2024) examined the effect of board diversity on the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The specific objective was to determine the effect of nationality diversity (BND), gender diversity of corporate board (BGD) and age diversity of corporate board members (BAD) on cash flow return on investment (CROI) of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, with firm size (FSZ) as the control variable. The study adopted ex-post facto research design on a population of twenty-one listed consumer goods firms on the Nigerian exchange group. The sample size of fifteen firms used in the study was determined through purposive sampling. Secondary data were sourced from the firms' annual reports over a period of ten (10) years, covering the years 2013 to 2022. Panel-corrected standard errors (PCSE) regression was applied in testing the hypotheses, which revealed that: Nationality diversity has a negative but insignificant effect on cash flow return on investment of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria (p -value = 3.59); Gender diversity has a positive but non-significant effect on the cash flow return on investment of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria (p -value = 0.080); Age diversity has a positive and significant effect on the cash flow return on investment of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria (p -value = 0.007). In conclusion, the negative impact of nationality diversity on cash flow return on investment shows the need for organizations to carefully manage the challenges associated with diverse national backgrounds, emphasizing effective communication and cultural alignment.

Aliyu, Danson and Abdullahi, (2024) investigated the effects of board diversity on the audit quality of publicly traded listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022. An ex-post facto research approach was used in this study. For data analysis, the panel regression technique was used in the study. The study's findings revealed that board independence and board financial expertise have a positive and significant effect on the audit quality of Nigerian listed consumer goods companies. However, board diversity had a negative and insignificant effect on the audit quality of Nigerian-listed consumer goods companies. The study concludes that boards with more independent members who are not influenced by management may improve the audit process efficacy. To improve audit quality, listed consumer goods firms should focus on retaining board independence and guaranteeing the presence of directors with significant financial experience. While the relationship between board diversity and audit quality is still uncertain, it is critical to promote diversity and inclusivity on corporate boards in order to build a more

robust governance structure. Continuous monitoring and research in this area will contribute to a better understanding of the relationship between board diversity and audit quality.

Ofor and Ibida (2021) investigated the effect of board diversity on firm performance of financial services companies in Nigeria. Secondary data were obtained from published financial reports and accounts of active Financial Services companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Limited (NGX) for ten years (2011 – 2020). The independent variables are Board Size, and Board Remuneration, while the dependent variable Firm Performance was proxied as Tobin Q (TOBQ). Null hypotheses were formulated for the study and secondary data obtained from the financial statements of the companies. The data were analysed using descriptive analysis, correlation matrix, and regression analysis. The Random Effects Generalized Least Square (GLS) regression result revealed that Board Size (BODS) and Board Remuneration (DRSA) all have significant effect on firm performance of Financial Services companies in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. Though Board Size (BODS) has an inverse effect. This research recommends that board diversity should be optimized with board size as this would scale up firm performance whilst optimizing resources.

Babatunde and Folorunsho (2020) examined the effect of board size and its independence on the performance of listed entities in Nigeria. It further determined the effect of board diligence and board diversity on the performance of quoted firms in Nigeria. These were with the view of examining the relationship that exists between board dichotomy and performance of quoted firms in Nigeria. The study which covered a ten-year period (2009–2018) made use of secondary data sourced from published annual reports and accounts of 35 purposively selected listed companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). The Pooled Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and Generalised least square method of regression techniques were employed in analyzing the data obtained. Findings from the study revealed that a significant negative relationship exists between earnings per share and board size with a coefficient of -0.33 and p-value of 0.0095 (>0.01) and between earnings per share and board diligence with coefficients of -0.43 and -0.48 and p-value of 0.02 (>0.05) and 0.0095 (>0.01) respectively, but no significant relationship exists between earnings per share and board independence with coefficients of -2.67 and -1.64 and p-value of 0.0218 and 0.49 respectively and between earnings per share and board gender diversity with coefficients of 0.06 and 0.08 and p-value of 0.42 and 0.36 respectively.

Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, (2025). Material management and productivity of Nigeria bottling appraised the material management and productivity of Nigerian Bottling Company. The population of the study was 288 staff. While two hundred and seventy (270) questionnaires were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Planning has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 14.027. Material procurement has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 33.048. Logistic has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 9.418. Stock and waste control has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha.

Nwangwu, Ohanyere; Nwangwu & Atueyi, (2025) examined the effect of artificial intelligent (AI) on decision-making in supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state, Nigeria. The study was anchored on Technology Acceptance Theory (TAT). A structure questionnaire was developed for data collection. The population of the study comprised of 281 management staff from thirteen (13) lubricant firms in Anambra State. Two hundred and sixty-nine (269) were duly filled and returned data was analysed using correlation analysis with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. Findings from the study show that. Machine learning has significant effect on decision support system on supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state ($T=2.244$, $P=0.006$). Neural networks has significant effect on creative decision skill on supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state ($T=9.790$, $P=0.009$). The study concludes that AI-powered predictive analytics improved decision-making in supply chain management in lubricant firms in Anambra state, Nigerian. The study recommends that Firms should prioritize data collection, storage, and analysis. Technical expertise is

critical for implementing and optimizing neural network algorithms. Firms should consider hiring experts or providing training to existing staff.

Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, (2025) examined job satisfaction and employee's performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state. The study investigated the relationship between reward, career development, staff training and recognition on employee performance. Relevant theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study was anchored on Herzberg's theory. The study collected data from primary and secondary sources. The population of the study comprised 478 staff of private universities in Anambra state. Formulated hypothesis were tested, using ANOVA. From the analysis, it was discovered that: Reward has significant effect on employee's performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state. Career advancement has significant effect on employee's performance, amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state. Training has significant effect on employees' performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state. In view of the findings,

Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Stephen, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, (2025) analyzed the financial literacy and its impact on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. The objective of the study was to; ascertain the effect of financial knowledge, financial behaviour and financial expertise on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. Three research hypotheses are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; Structured questionnaire were used to gather information from the population. The population of the study is made of youths from age 20-39 in South East zone of Nigeria, which is 50,222,32 target population. It comprises of all the youths in South East Nigeria, while the sample size is 399 were gotten through Taro Yamane formula. The researcher distributes three hundred and ninety-nine (399) questionnaires but only three hundred and seventy-three (373) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Correlation and t-test method of data analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The finding of the study shows that; Financial knowledge has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. Financial behaviour has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

Ntadom, Atueyi & Jacobs (2021). examined the effect of career development on organizational performance, a Study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. The study was anchored on Self-concept theory of career development. As a cross-sectional survey the research design were used, a structured questionnaire instrument were developed and used for data collection by the researcher to which reflect such options as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree, which is popularly referred as five (5) points likert scale. It was used to obtain information from the respondents. The population of the study comprised of 57, 710 students selected across the five south east states of Nigeria. A sample size of 399 students was drawn from the population, using Taro Yamane formula of which three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaires were duly completed and returned; showing 96% response rate. Research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA regression analysis which was carried out with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. The study found that career development has significant effect on Organizational Performance.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Ex-post facto research with an emphasis on secondary data was used in this study. *Ex-post* facto research design entails gathering and evaluating data regarding certain variables that are pre-existing. *Ex-post* facto research designs are consequently preferred because they use secondary data that doesn't require manipulation.

3.2 Nature and Sources of Data

A panel data set from the annual reports and financial statements of companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group were used in the study. The 12 years of the panel's coverage, from 2012 to 2023, was twelve years. This data collection is secondary.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of all the consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange limited for the period of 2012–2023. As at 31st December 2023, the total number of consumer goods firm were twenty-eight (28). They are as follows, Cadbury Nigeria, Champion Breweries, Dangote Flour Mills, Dangote Sugar Refinery, Ellah Lakes, Flour Mills Of Nigeria, FTN Cocoa Processors, Golden Guinea Breweries, Guinness Nigeria, Honeywell Flour Mill, International Breweries, Livestock Feeds, McNichols, Morison Industries, Multi-Trex Integrated Foods, Nascon Allied Industries, Nestle Nigeria, Nigerian Breweries, Nigerian Enamelware, Northern Nigeria Flour Mills, Okomu Oil Palm, Presco, PZ Cussons Nigeria, 7-Up Bottling Company, Unilever Nigeria. Union Dicon Salt, Vitafoam Nigeria, ABC Transport

3.4 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study selected ten companies, including Dangote Flour Mills, International Breweries, Nascon Allied Industries, Nestle Nigeria, PZ Cussons Nigeria, Okomu Oil Palm, Presco, Nigeria, 7-Up Bottling Company, Unilever Nigeria, and ABC Transport, based on publicly available financial statements for a ten-year period spanning from 2012 to 2023. This was done because the number of consumer goods firms listed is excessively large. The chosen companies are based those that consistently reported comprehensive data on board diversity and performance from 2012 to 2023

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

Panel Least Square (PLS) was selected for the study based on its ideal features, which include neutrality, adequate, least variance, linearity, and mean square. These characteristics demonstrate that the estimators' traits can be attained using a variety of methods; nevertheless, the Panel Least Square (PLS) estimates stood out as the best when compared to other linear estimates from different econometric techniques due to their minimal variance property. The PLS approach is very popular because of this specific small least variance characteristic.

3.6 Model Specification

To confirm the impact of the board diversity on consumer goods firms' performance in Nigeria, a model will be created. The strategy is to alter the model by defining board diversity multiple regression equation as a function of performance. The research altered the model of Eluyela, et al. (2019), which looked at how the gender dichotomy affected dividend distribution policies in publicly traded financial services companies in Nigeria.

The model is stated thus:

$$Dip=(FD, FA, BZ) \text{ -----(i)}$$

Where

Dividend policy

Female directors

Firm age

Board size

The model will be modified to enable us look at the topic from another dimension. Thus we will state our modified model as:

The model to be regressed in this study will be presented in a relational form as follows

$$ROA=(AGD, GDD, ETD, FRD,) \text{ -----(ii)}$$

Where

ROA = Return on Assets

AGD = Age diversity

GDD = Gender diversity

ETD= Ethnicity diversity

FRD = Foreign Diversity

F=Functional notation

3.7 Variables and their Measurement

s/n	Variables	Measurement	Sources
1	ROA	Firm's net income to total assets in the same year	(Setiawan & Gestanti, 2022)
2	<i>Independent variables</i> Age diversity	Any firm above 10 years is 1, below is 0	Appah (2023)
3	Gender diversity	Ratio of female to male	Ejiofor, (2024)
4	Ethnic diversity	If all the tribes (Igbo, Hausa, Yourba) are represented 1, if not 0	Ejiofor, (2024)
5	Foreign Diversity	If the director is Nigerian 0, if foreigner 1	Okeke (2023)

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTEPRETATION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive statistics for the dependent and independent variables used in this study were presented in table 4.1 below:

Table 4.1: Summary of descriptive statistics for the variables employed in this study:

	ROA	AGD	GDD	ETD	FRD
Mean	0.099750	2.000000	5.716667	0.458333	2.158333
Median	0.030000	2.000000	6.000000	0.000000	2.000000
Maximum	0.610000	0.000000	3.000000	1.000000	1.000000
Minimum	0.010000	1.000000	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Std. Dev.	0.124586	0.799159	0.452506	0.500350	0.744682
Skewness	1.643503	0.099202	-0.961645	0.167248	-0.262014
Kurtosis	5.435203	1.828255	1.924761	1.027972	1.849480
Jarque-Bera	83.67314	7.061755	24.27591	20.00391	7.991513
Probability	0.000000	0.029279	0.000005	0.000045	0.018394
Sum	11.97000	240.0000	686.0000	55.00000	259.0000
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.847092	76.00000	24.36667	29.79167	65.99167
Observations	120	120	120	120	120

Source: Researchers' computation (2025)

Note: *1% level of significance **5% level of significance

The variables' lowest, median, and maximum values are displayed in the table together with the descriptive statistics of the mean, standard deviation, and Jarque-Bera (JB) Statistics normalcy test. For an 12-year period between 2012 and 2023, the study used 120 firms years data observations of yearly reports from the Nigerian Exchange Limited. Return on assets is the dependent variable, and Age diversity, gender diversity, ethnic diversity and foreign diversity are the independent factors, according to the table above. The summary statistics reveal that the average means of return on assets, Age diversity, gender diversity, ethnic diversity and foreign diversity are 0.099750, 2.000000, 5.716667, 0.458333 and 2.158333 respectively. The standard deviations of these firm factor variables are 0.124586, 0.799159, 0.452506, 0.500350, and 0.744682, respectively. The standard deviation figures show that the board diversity variables in Nigeria are widely distributed. For instance, Return on Asset (ROA) values, which are 0.61 and 0.01, respectively. In a similar vein, the age diversity was 0 at minimum and 1 at the maximum. These fluctuations in age diversity are a little on the low side. The highest is 3.00 and the minimum is 1.00 even when it comes to gender diversity. It has also been noted that gender diversity

changed significantly over time. Ethnic diversity has a maximum value of 1.000 and a minimum value of 0.00. The significant volatility over time suggests a high degree of ethnicity variable variability, which impacts performance. The difference between the highest and lowest performance values of the chosen consumer goods firms showed that the sampled firms are homogeneous and that the heteroscedasticity issue should not be taken into account by the chosen estimation methodologies.

Last but not least, table 4.1's Jarque–Bera (JB) test, which looks for abnormalities or extreme values among the variables, reveals that age diversity, ethnic diversity and foreign diversity have a normally distributed distribution at the 5% level of significance, while performance have a 1% level of significance. This indicates that, even in the unlikely event that there are any outlier variables, the conclusions will not be distorted and may be relied upon for making generalizations. Overall, the descriptive statistics showed that the data did not contain any outliers or bias in the sample selection that would have hampered the study's ability to be generalized. This also justifies the use of panel Least Square estimation techniques. Hence, any recommendations made to a very large extent would represent the characteristics of the true population of study.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Finding the degree of relationship between the variables and identifying any multi-collinearity issues are the two main goals of utilizing a correlation matrix. Shukeri and Islam (2012) cite Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) as saying that the problem of multi-collinearity ends if independent variables have a strong or perfect correlation with each other, with correlation values reaching 0.90%. In order to ascertain the type or degree of association, that is, a positive or negative correlation, as well as the significance of the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables, Pearson's correlation matrix was used to examine the degree of association between the board diversity and performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Therefore, in examining the association among the variables, we employed the Pearson correlation coefficient (correlation matrix) and the results are presented in the table 4.2 below.

Table 4.2 Result of Pearson Correlation Matrix

	ROA	AGD	GDD	ETD	FRD
ROA	1.000000	-0.285285	0.202470	-0.091162	0.167995
AGD	-0.285285	1.000000	-0.065263	-0.184741	0.054616
GDD	0.202470	-0.065263	1.000000	0.138084	0.203071
ETD	-0.091162	-0.184741	0.138084	1.000000	0.232110
FRD	0.167995	0.054616	0.203071	0.232110	1.000000

Source: Researcher's summary of correlation analysis (2025).

Return on asset have a negative association with the variables Age diversity (AGD) and ethnic diversity (ETD), but a positive correlation with Gender diversity (GDD) and foreign Diversity (FRD), according to the correlation matrix table. The aforementioned findings demonstrate that there is a significant and negative correlation (ROA/AGD=-0.28) between Return on asset and Age diversity. Additionally, a significant and negative correlation (ROA/ETD = -0.09) has been found between the value of return on asset and ethnicity. There is a substantial and positive correlation between return on asset and board size (ROA & GDD) = 0.20. Female directors and board size have a significant and negative correlation (AGE/GDD=-0.28/0.20). Additionally, a negative and substantial correlation between AGD and ETD (-0.28/-0.09) was noted. However, none of the variables were found to be less than 0.90. That is, no two exploratory variables had a perfect correlation. The highest correlation is between two variables which are highly correlated with (AGD=0.20) which indicate that multi co linearity is not a serious problem that would distort the regression result in the model used for analysis. All of the factors have a strong link with return on assets, according to a detailed examination of the Pearson correlation coefficient values. Therefore, in checking for multicollinearity problem, the study noticed from the correlation table above that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated and thereby ruled out the case of having an outlier. This indicates the absence of multi-collinearity problem in the model used for the analysis. This also justifies the use of the Panel Least Square (PLS)

4.3 Result Interpretation

In order to examine the relationship between the dependent variable (Return on Assets) and the independent variables (AGD, GDD, ETD and FRD) and to test the formulated hypothesis, we employed a Panel Regression Analysis since the data had both time series (2012-2023) and longitudinal properties (10 quoted consumer firms) our analysis is presented in table 4.5 below

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AGD_{it} + \beta_2 GDD_{it} + \beta_3 ETD_{it} + \beta_4 FRD_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Table 4.3: Summary of regression result

Dependent Variable: ROA
 Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random effects)
 Date: 04/19/25 Time: 03:18
 Sample: 2012 2023
 Periods included: 12
 Cross-sections included: 10
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 120
 Swamy and Arora estimator of component variances

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.064448	0.106665	2.604214	0.0069
AGD	0.019156	0.008670	2.209295	0.0291
GDD	0.000458	0.016129	3.028415	0.0004
ETD	0.020334	0.014305	1.421465	0.1579
FRD	0.039638	0.009941	3.987405	0.0001
Effects Specification				
			S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random			0.133409	0.7710
Idiosyncratic random			0.072715	0.2290
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.696563	Mean dependent var	0.015504	
Adjusted R-squared	0.659349	S.D. dependent var	0.076609	
S.E. of regression	0.071581	Sum squared resid	0.589241	
F-statistic	5.325859	Durbin-Watson stat	1.648114	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000569			
Unweighted Statistics				
R-squared	18.71776	Mean dependent var	0.099750	
Sum squared resid	1.750814	Durbin-Watson stat	0.554677	

Source: Researcher’s summary of correlation analysis (2025).

The results presented above will be analyzed using two criteria; Accounting a priori criteria, and statistical criteria

A. Accounting a priori Criteria

The a’p priori expectation is used to determine the existing Accounting theories and this indicates the signs and magnitude of our variables.

1. A regression line intercept of 0.064448 is displayed in the result in table 4.3. With a p-value of 0.0069, which is greater than 0.05, the t-test result is 2.604214, which is positive and statistically significant. This suggests that when there is no change in the explanatory variables, the return on assets will remain constant at 69% per cent annually.

2. Table 4.3's regression result demonstrates a statistically significant positive correlation between return on assets and Age diversity. Age diversity have a value of 0.019219, which suggests that a 19% increase in Age diversity will, *ceteris paribus*, result in a 19% improvement in business performance. This is in line with the *apriori* prediction. This finding bolsters the theory that raising Age diversity will improve assets' perceptions of firm performance and value.
3. There is a positive relationship between return on asset and gender diversity. The gender diversity value is 3.028415. This suggests that a percent increase in the gender diversity will, *ceteris paribus*, result in a rise in return on asset value of roughly by three percent. This is in line with the *apriori* prediction. This finding corroborates the theory that larger gender diversity in Nigeria do better than smaller ones.
4. There is a positive relationship between ethnic diversity and return on asset. With a ethnic diversity value of 0.020334, an increase of one percent is expected to result in a performance rise of roughly two percent, *ceteris paribus*. This is in line with the *apriori* prediction. This finding bolsters the hypothesis that raising ethnicity diversity will enhance consumer goods firm performance in Nigeria.
5. There is a positive relationship between foreign diversity and return on assets. The foreign diversity value is 0.039638, which suggests that a 1% increase in foreign diversity will, *ceteris paribus*, result in a 3% rise in return on assets. This is in line with the *apriori* prediction. This finding confirms that increases in foreign diversity will increases the performance of consumer goods firms' value in Nigeria.

B. Statistical Criteria

The age diversity showed positive and significant results, with a t-value of 2.209295 and a p-value of 0.0291, respectively. Their p-value was less than the 5% level of significance, which explains that age diversity has positive significant effect on performance of consumer goods firms value in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the value that gender diversity place on consumer goods firm is positively correlated with the return on asset. Their t-value of 3.028415 and p-value of 0.0004, which was less than the five percent level of significance, respectively, demonstrated this. This finding indicates that variations in the return on assets of consumer goods firms in Nigeria are significantly influenced by the gender diversity of the board.

The return on assets of consumer goods firms in Nigeria is positively but not significantly impacted by the ethnicity. The p-value of 0.1579 was below than the five percent criterion of significance, According to this finding, ethnicity show insignificant effect on return on assets

In Nigeria, foreign directives have significant and positive impact on return on assets. Their t-value of 3.987405 and p-value of 0.0001 indicated this, with the latter being less than five percent significance level. This finding indicates that changes in the performance of return on assets of consumer goods firm in Nigeria are significantly influenced by foreign directives. Based on the outcome, the coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.696563, meaning that the independent variables in the model—age diversity, gender diversity, ethnic diversity and foreign diversity—explain 69% of the variation in return on assets. Conversely, factors outside of our model account for roughly 31% of the total. This demonstrates even more how well the model fits the data.

The associated probability value of 0.000569 indicates that the model's f-statistics value of 5.325859, which measures the combined importance of the explanatory variables, is judged to be statistically significant at the 1 percent level. This suggests that the dependent and independent variables differ significantly from one another.

4.4 Hypotheses Testing

The need to examine the relationship between the actual results data and the stated hypothesis has called for this section. This result will be compared with the statistical criteria to see if the preconceived notion in this research work holds or not. However, if the probability value is less than 0.05%, alternative hypothesis is accepted, but when it is greater than 5% hull hypothesis is accepted

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Age diversity has no significant effect on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. From the result report of our t-test in table 4.3 above, it was observed from Age diversity, the value of 2.209295 with the probability of 0.0291 which is not within the desired level of significant (0.05), we therefore reject null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that Age diversity has significant effect on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Gender diversity affects the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria

From the forgoing result we find out that computed value for Gender diversity is 3.028415 while its probability is 0.0004 this shown that the gender diversity is statistically significant. Based on this analysis we reject (H₀) and accept (H₁), which implies that gender diversity affects the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Ethnic diversity has no significant effect on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Drawing inference from our regression result in table 4.3, we found that the value of Ethnic diversity is 1.421465 while its probability is 0.1579 this shows that Ethnic diversity has significant effect on the return on asset of consumer goods firm in Nigeria. We therefore accept the null hypothesis which states that Ethnic diversity has no significant effect on performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria

Hypothesis Four

Ho₄: Foreign diversity has no significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. From table 4.3 above, we find out that t-statistics value for Foreign diversity is 3.987405 while its probability is 0.0001 this showed that the Foreign diversity is positive and statistically significant. Based on this analysis we reject (H₀) and accept (H₁), which implies that Foreign diversity has significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The study examines the effect of board diversity and performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The main goal of a firm is to increase the performance by increasing the value of a firm. Maximizing return on assets is essential for a company because it means increasing the prosperity of shareholders as well, which becomes the company's main goal. *Ex-post* facto research with an emphasis on secondary data was used in this study. A panel data set from the annual reports and financial statements of companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group were used in the study. This study concentrated on consumer goods companies in Nigeria that are listed by Nigeria Exchange group (NEG), as this is where the information needed for an in-depth examination would come from. The population of this study consists of all the consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange limited for the period of 2012–2023. In this study, the regression approach of data analysis was used. The study found that age diversity has significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria; gender diversity has significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria; Ethnic diversity has no significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria; Foreign diversity has significant effect on the performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that board diversity has significant positive effect on performance of consumer goods forms in Nigeria.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made as follows:

- i. The management of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria should continue to balance the level of age diversity in order to improve their return on assets and balance decision value.
- ii. Gender diversity should be increased between 3-4 members for improved quality and quick decision making in relation to performance
- iii. Ethnic representations on the board will be good since many studies show that board ethnic and international diversity improves firm performance.

- iv. The member of foreign diversity in the board of directors in quoted consumer goods firms should be increased in order to bring professional skills and expertise to boost the managerial capacity and capital accessibility of the consumer firms in Nigeria.

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